

Dissociation Constants of some Inorganic Acids from Solubility Measurements.

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In previous papers (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1913, **19**, 407 ; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **35**, 800 ; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **107**, 824 ; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, **153**, 323 ; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 585), we have shown that the dissociation constants of weak acids can be calculated from the measurements of the solubility of sparingly soluble weak acids (*e.g.*, benzoic, cinnamic, boric, arsenious, carbonic, etc.) in sodium or potassium salts of the acids of which we want to determine the dissociation constants.

In this communication we are recording the results of solubility measurements with benzoic, carbonic, arsenious and boric acids in sodium or potassium salts of hypophosphorous, phosphorous, chromic, hydrofluoric, iodic, titanio, antimonio, boric, vanadio, tungstic and molybdic acids.

From these solubility measurements we can get an idea about the dissociation constants of these acids. Moreover, we have critically discussed the principle of this method of determining the dissociation constants of acids and deduced a general formula.

The experimental results are recorded in the following tables, where a = solubility of the sparingly soluble acid in water, b = the solubility of the same acid in sodium or potassium salt of the acid of which the dissociation constant has to be determined, c = original concentration of the salt solution, K = dissociation constant of the unknown acid, and K_1 = dissociation constant of the known acid. In the case of the dibasic acids, only the second dissociation constants are obtained by this method (*cf.* Datta and Dhar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **107**, 824).

TABLE I.

Hypophosphorous Acid (Sodium Hypophosphite Solution used).

(i) *Dissociation constant with benzoic acid ($K_1 = 6 \times 10^{-5}$) at 17°.*

a	b	c	$b-a$	$c-b+a$	K
0.0220	0.0350	0.8454	0.0130	0.8323	6.5×10^{-5}
,,	0.0320	0.5918	0.0100	0.5818	7.6×10^{-5}
,,	0.0300	0.4227	0.008	0.4147	8.5×10^{-5}
,,	0.0270	0.2536	0.005	0.2486	1.8×10^{-5}

(ii) *With carbonic acid gas* ($K_1 = 3 \times 10^{-7}$).

Temp.	a	b	c	b-a	c-b+a	K
27°	0.05204	0.0703	0.1467	0.00826	0.1384	3.7×10^{-6}
25°	0.06582	0.08554	0.0698	0.01972	0.05008	4.2×10^{-6}
„	„	0.0786	0.4849	0.01278	0.4721	5.7×10^{-6}
„	„	0.0745	0.2424	0.00868	0.2337	6×10^{-6}

The above results are sufficient to indicate that the dissociation constant increases with the fall of concentration of salt solutions. The dissociation constant with carbon dioxide has a much smaller value than with benzoic acid. Hence the dissociation constant appears to be lowered as a weaker acid is used for determining the dissociation constant.

These results show that hypophosphorous acid is stronger than phosphorous acid. This relation is also observable from the following electric conductivity measurements:—

TABLE II.

Dilution	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
Molecular conductivity (H_3PO_3)	245	281	312	335	352	361	367
Molecular conductivity (H_4PO_4)	222	257	292	318	337	351	358

(Mellor—'Inorganic & Theoretical Chemistry,' 1928, Vol. VIII, p. 903).

TABLE III.

Phosphorous Acid (Sodium Phosphite Solution used.)

(i) *Dissociation constant with benzoic acid at 17°.*

a	b	c	b-a	c-b+a	K
0.0220	0.4860	1.8060	0.4640	1.3420	8.25×10^{-6}
„	0.2930	0.9030	0.2710	0.6320	1.13×10^{-6}
„	0.2490	0.7224	0.2270	0.4954	1.27×10^{-6}
„	0.1710	0.4515	0.1490	0.3035	1.79×10^{-6}

(ii) *Dissociation constant with carbonic acid.*

Temp.	a	b	c	b-a	c-b+a	K
24°	0.0679	0.2337	0.7692	1.1658	0.60	4.4×10^{-7}
"	"	0.2055	0.3846	0.1376	0.2469	2.8×10^{-7}
21°	0.07454	0.2395	0.6153	0.1549	0.4604	4.2×10^{-7}
"	"	0.1945	0.4615	0.1199	0.3415	5.1×10^{-7}
26.5°	0.0630	0.2322	2.2015	0.1692	2.0323	1.3×10^{-7}

TABLE IV.

Chromic Acid.

(i) *Dissociation constant with carbonic acid at 30° (assuming complete ionisation of potassium dichromate).*

a	b	c	b-a	c-b+a	K
0.05714	0.3684	1.000	0.3112	0.6880	1.9×10^{-7}
"	0.2601	0.500	0.2029	0.2971	1.23×10^{-7}
"	0.1973	0.250	0.1402	0.1098	9.5×10^{-8}
"	0.1500	0.1250	0.0928	0.0322	6.4×10^{-8}
"	0.2541	0.3962	0.1970	0.1992	8.6×10^{-8}
"	0.2460	0.3432	0.1880	0.1594	7.6×10^{-8}
"	0.2637	0.4309	0.2066	0.2243	9.0×10^{-8}
"	0.1760	0.2154	0.1188	0.0966	1.1×10^{-7}
"	0.2143	0.2396	0.1572	0.0824	5.7×10^{-8}

We have also worked with benzoic and boric acids. In the case of arsenious acid, the solution becomes green due to the reduction of the chromate. With benzoic, the chromate was converted into dichromate.

(ii) *Dissociation constant with boric acid at 30° (K₁ for boric acid = 6.4×10^{-10} , Lunden, *J. Chim. phys.*, 1907, 5, 10; (K₁ = 5.7×10^{-10} , Menzel, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1922, 100, 295.)*

a	b	c	b-a	c-b+a	K
1.029	1.238	0.1017	0.209	Negative	...
"	1.213	0.09457	0.184	Negative	...
"	1.133	0.04728	0.084	Negative	...
"	1.035	0.01017	0.006	0.00147	7.6×10^{-8}
"	1.035	0.009457	0.006	0.003457	6.3×10^{-8}

The above and other negative results will be discussed later on. Hence the second dissociation constant of chromic acid is very small.

(iii) *Dissociation constant with benzoic acid at 30°.*

<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>b-a</i>	<i>c-b+a</i>	<i>K</i>
0.03147	0.1145	0.1704	0.08303	0.08737	3.1×10^{-5}
„	0.08514	0.1155	0.05367	0.06183	4×10^{-5}
„	0.0841	0.1076	0.05263	0.05497	3.7×10^{-5}
„	0.08152	0.1017	0.05005	0.05165	3.8×10^{-5}
„	0.0774	0.09457	0.04593	0.04864	4.3×10^{-5}
„	0.06812	0.0742	0.03665	0.03755	5.2×10^{-5}
„	0.06295	0.06531	0.03148	0.03383	6×10^{-5}

It is to be observed that *K* by this method has much larger value than that obtained with carbon dioxide. Also the dissociation constant increases with the dilution.

TABLE V.

Hydrofluoric Acid (Potassium Fluoride Solution used).

(i) *Dissociation constant with benzoic acid at 30°.*

<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>b-a</i>	<i>c-b+a</i>	<i>K</i>
0.03204	0.1361	1.191	0.1040	1.0870	1.88×10^{-4}
„	0.1168	0.9528	0.08476	0.8680	2.9×10^{-4}
„	0.09689	0.7146	0.06485	0.6498	2.9×10^{-4}
„	0.07442	0.4764	0.04238	0.4337	3.2×10^{-4}
0.03147	0.04231	0.04017	0.01084	0.02933	4.7×10^{-4}
„	0.04076	0.02678	0.00929	0.01749	3.8×10^{-4}

(ii) *Dissociation constant with boric acid at 30°.*

<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>b-a</i>	<i>c-b+a</i>	<i>K</i>
1.029	1.566	0.3287	0.537	Negative	<i>x</i>
„	1.330	0.1643	0.301	„	<i>x</i>
„	1.205	0.08217	0.176	„	<i>x</i>

(iii) *Dissociation constant with arsenious acid at 30°.*(Compare von Zawadzki, *Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 1427 ; $K_1 = 2 \times 10^{-10}$).

<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>b</i> - <i>a</i>	<i>c</i> - <i>b</i> + <i>a</i>	<i>K</i>
0.0284	0.2936	0.08215	0.0096	0.07257	2.2×10^{-8}
„	0.3026	0.1643	0.0186	0.1557	1.27×10^{-8}
„	0.3096	0.9287	0.0256	0.3081	1.28×10^{-8}

(iv) *Dissociation constant with carbonic acid gas.*

Temp.	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>b</i> - <i>a</i>	<i>c</i> - <i>b</i> + <i>a</i>	<i>K</i>
28°	0.06127	0.1504	1.236	0.08913	1.1488	2.6×10^{-8}
„	„	0.1295	0.619	0.06823	0.5506	2.2×10^{-8}
30°	0.05714	0.1320	0.9904	0.07486	0.9155	3.0×10^{-8}
„	„	0.1156	0.7428	0.05846	0.6843	3.7×10^{-8}

It will be seen that in all these cases dissociation constant increases with dilution and weaker the acid used, the smaller is the dissociation constant obtained with it. Hence hydrofluoric acid is much weaker than the other halogen acids.

TABLE VI.

Iodic Acid (Potassium Iodate Solution was used).(i) *Dissociation constant with carbonic acid at 19°.*

<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>b</i> - <i>a</i>	<i>c</i> - <i>b</i> + <i>a</i>	<i>K</i>
0.07886	0.08373	0.3437	0.00487	0.3388	3.88×10^{-4}
„	0.08164	0.13748	0.00278	0.1347	4.1×10^{-4}
0.06541 (18°)	0.09505	0.6874	0.00864	0.67876	2.1×10^{-4}

Hence iodic acid appears to be weaker than chloric acid, because the solubility of carbon dioxide in a solution of potassium chlorate is the same as in water. There was no increase in the solubility of benzoic acid in solutions of potassium iodate.

TABLE VII.

Titanic Acid (Potassium Titanate Solution used).

Kahlbaum's potassium titanate was washed with alcohol to remove any free alkali. The salt is only sparingly soluble in water and the solution is alkaline indicating that it is appreciably hydrolysed.

(i) *Dissociation constant with benzoic acid at 18°.*

<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>b</i> - <i>a</i>	<i>c</i> - <i>b</i> + <i>a</i>	<i>K</i>
0·0226	0·0240	0·00550	0·0014	0·00410	$2·8 \times 10^{-3}$
„	0·0234	0·004125	0·0008	0·003325	$7·0 \times 10^{-3}$
„	0·0232	0·00275	0·0006	0·002150	$8·1 \times 10^{-3}$
„	0·0230	0·001375	0·0004	0·000975	$8·2 \times 10^{-3}$

The dissociation constant increases with dilution. It is to be observed that the saturated solution of potassium titanate has the strength about *N*/200.

(ii) *Dissociation constant with carbonic acid.*

<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>b</i> - <i>a</i>	<i>c</i> - <i>b</i> + <i>a</i>	<i>K</i>
0·07886 (19°)	0·1149	0·0050	0·0361	Negative	<i>x</i>
0·08377 (17°)	0·09585	0·0035	0·01208	„	<i>x</i>
„	0·08954	0·0015	0·00477	„	<i>x</i>

Due to the alkaline nature of the solution of potassium titanate the solubility of carbonic acid gas is tremendously increased giving rise to negative results. Hence titanitic acid appears to be a comparatively weak acid. No electric conductivity measurement is, however, available for this acid.

TABLE VIII.

Antimonic Acid (Solution of $K_2H_2Sb_2O_7$ was used).(i) *Dissociation constant with benzoic acid at 18°.*

<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>b</i> - <i>a</i>	<i>c</i> - <i>b</i> + <i>a</i>	<i>K</i>
0·0226	0·0240	0·010	0·0014	0·0086	$5·9 \times 10^{-3}$
„	0·0237	0·0075	0·0011	0·0064	$7·1 \times 10^{-3}$
„	0·0234	0·0050	0·0008	0·0042	$8·9 \times 10^{-3}$
„	0·0230	0·0025	0·0004	0·0021	$1·78 \times 10^{-2}$

This salt is sparingly soluble and the saturated solution at 18° has the strength about *N*/50. From the dissociation constant it is clear that it increases as in previous cases with dilution.

(ii) *Dissociation constant with carbonic acid gas.*

Temp.	a	b	c	b-a	c-b+a	K
20°	0.07654	0.09173	0.020	0.01519	0.00481	4.79×10^{-7}
21°	0.07432	0.08191	0.010	0.00769	0.00241	9.3×10^{-7}
22°	0.07213	0.07682	0.005	0.00469	0.00081	2.9×10^{-7}

Antimonic acid also appears to be a weak acid.

TABLE IX.

Boric Acid (Borax was used).

 (i) *Dissociation constant with benzoic acid at 18°.*

a	b	c	b-a	c-b+a	K
0.0226	0.710	0.4	0.6874	Negative	x
„	0.540	0.3	0.5174	„	x
„	0.380	0.2	0.3574	„	x
„	0.180	0.1	0.1574	„	x

 (ii) *Dissociation constant with carbonic acid gas.*

Temp.	a	b	c	b-a	c-b+a	K
16°	0.08641	0.4218	0.2156	0.3349	„	x
16°	0.08641	0.2664	0.0924	0.1800	„	x
17°	0.08377	0.3470	0.1540	0.2633	Negative	x
18°	0.08123	0.5288	0.3080	0.4457	„	x

These negative results with boric acid show that it is a very weak acid, and these solubility measurements support the conclusion from electric conductivity determination.

TABLE IX.

Vanadic Acid (Sodium Vanadate Solution used).

In case of carbonic acid gas we get negative results and the solution of vanadate which was originally colourless becomes yellow due to the liberation of vanadic acid.

(i) *Dissociation constant with benzoic acid at 17°.*

<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>b-a</i>	<i>c-b+a</i>	<i>K</i>
0.0220	0.02825	0.1247	0.00625	0.11845	4×10^{-3}
„	0.02600	0.09345	0.0040	0.08945	7.4×10^{-3}
„	0.02450	0.06235	0.0025	0.05985	1.26×10^{-2}
„	0.02350	0.03117	0.0015	0.02967	1.74×10^{-2}

The dissociation constant goes on increasing with dilution.

(ii) *Dissociation constant with carbonic acid gas at 21°.*

<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>b-a</i>	<i>c-b+a</i>	<i>K</i>
0.07427	0.7177	0.4646	0.6434	Negative	x
„	0.5944	0.3117	0.5201	„	x

TABLE X.

Tungstic Acid (Sodium Tungstate Solution used).(i) *Dissociation constant with benzoic acid at 30°.*

<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>b-a</i>	<i>c-b+a</i>	<i>K</i>
0.03204	0.07207	0.09980	0.04003	0.05977	7.1×10^{-5}
„	0.06935	0.09050	0.03731	0.05319	7.3×10^{-5}
„	0.06646	0.08014	0.03442	0.04572	7.4×10^{-5}
„	0.07287	0.1012	0.04083	0.06036	6.96×10^{-5}
„	0.06046	0.06072	0.02842	0.03232	7.6×10^{-5}
„	0.04738	0.0253	0.01520	0.01010	7.4×10^{-5}

(ii) *Dissociation constant with arsenious acid at 30°.*

<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>b-a</i>	<i>c-b+a</i>	<i>K</i>
0.284	0.5431	0.08014	0.261	Negative	x
„	0.4331	0.04043	0.1491	Negative	x

TABLE XII.

Molybdic Acid.(i) *Dissociation constant with carbonic acid in ammonium molybdate.*

Temp.	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>b-a</i>	<i>c-b+a</i>	<i>K</i>
23°	0.0700	0.0841	0.600	0.01410	0.4857	5.1×10^{-6}
22°	0.07213	0.0893	0.250	0.01717	0.2428	1.2×10^{-6}
20°5'	0.07581	0.08654	0.125	0.01073	0.1142	2.2×10^{-6}

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(ii) *Dissociation constant with carbonic acid in potassium molybdate at 25°.*

a	b	c	b-a	c-b+a	K
0·06583	0·1686	0·4096	0·1027	0·3068	$5·7 \times 10^{-7}$
"	0·1200	0·2048	0·05418	0·1506	1×10^{-6}
"	0·0951	0·1024	0·02928	0·0781	$4·8 \times 10^{-6}$
"	0·0802	0·04096	0·01438	0·0265	$3·6 \times 10^{-6}$

(ii) *Dissociation constant with benzoic acid in potassium molybdate solution at 30°.*

a	b	c	b-a	c-b+a	K
0·03204	0·06967	0·06568	0·03763	0·02805	$3·8 \times 10^{-5}$
"	0·05766	0·03978	0·02562	0·01414	$4·1 \times 10^{-5}$
"	0·04805	0·02386	0·01601	0·00785	$5·89 \times 10^{-5}$
"	0·05365	0·03284	0·02161	0·01123	$4·62 \times 10^{-5}$
"	0·08038	0·07729	0·04884	0·02848	$2·3 \times 10^{-5}$

It will be observed that as dilution increases, the dissociation constant also increases.

The foregoing experimental results obtained with vanadic, tungstic and molybdic acids show that they are weak acids. With molybdic acid Grossmann and Kramer (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 1606) obtained the following results:—

Dilution	...	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
Molecular conductivity(25°)		95·8	129·5	147·5	155·6	160·6	163·6	169

Walden ("Das Leitvermögen der Elektrolyte," 1924, II, p. 117) has recorded the following results with tungstic acid at 25°:—

Dilution	...	32	64	128	256	512	1024
Molecular conductivity ...		176·4	233·5	279·1	325·2	371·6	416·7

It should be emphasised that all these acids in aqueous solutions exist partly in the colloidal state.

Discussion.

From the foregoing results it will be observed that—

(1) The formula $K = \frac{K_1 \times a (c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$ breaks down in some cases specially when the acid used for determining the dissociation constant is polybasic and that we get negative results.

(2) The dissociation constant goes on increasing with the dilution of the salt solution. In other words, the solubility of the acid falls off more rapidly than the concentration of the salt solution.

(3) The weaker the acid used, the lower is the value of the dissociation constant of the unknown acid.

In deducing the dissociation constants we have applied the formula

$$K = \frac{K_1 \times a(c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$$

The assumptions in this formula are:—

(a) The sodium or potassium salt is completely ionised.

(b) The acids of which the dissociation constants are K and K_1 are so weak that their ionisation is negligible.

Although the second assumption is generally true, the first is not exact and corrections are necessary.

The above formula has been deduced irrespective of the basicity of the acid of which K_1 we assume. From the viewpoint of the basicity of the acid the applicability of the formula is open to question and corrections are necessary. In deducing this formula we have considered the following equation:—

In the above relation the acids concerned are fortunately monobasic and we shall try to prove that the formula is specific for monobasic acids of which K_1 we assume, and it can be deduced from the general formula which will be considered now. The basicity of the acid of which dissociation constant is required has very little to do in changing the relation, provided it is assumed that the salt of this acid ionises completely and that the acids do not ionise, which is only partially true. We shall now proceed to derive a general formula.

Let the acid of which K_1 we assume be H_nB , where n is the basicity of the acid. Let H_mA be the acid whose dissociation constant is required, where m is its basicity.

Then the sodium salt of the acid H_nB will be Na_nB and of H_mA will be Na_mA , then

Let the solubility of H_nB in water = a and in Na_mA solution of concentration $c = b$.

Let k_1, k_2, k_3 and k_4 be the degrees of ionisation of $Na_mA, H_nB, Na_{m-1}HA$ and $H_{n-1}NaB$ respectively.

Now the excess = $b - a$ of the acid H_nB dissolving in the solution of Na_mA of concentration c will ionise as

Hence the concentration of H ions that go to form $H_{n-1}NaB$ will be $(b-a)/n$. Hence the concentration of $Na_{m-1}HA$ formed = $(b-a)/n$.

Now the dissociation constant of the acid H_nB is given by

$$K = \frac{H \times H_{n-1}B}{H_nB}$$

but as the solution is always saturated with H_nB , the concentration of $H_nB = a$. But a part of it also ionises and hence the concentration of H_nB undissociated

$$= H_nB - k_2 H_nB = (1 - k_2) H_nB = (1 - k_2) a$$

Also the concentration of $H_{n-1}B$ will be given by $H_{n-1}NaB$, which will ionise as

Hence the concentration of $H_{n-1}B' = k_4(b-a)/n$.

$$K = \frac{H^\circ \times k_4(b-a)/n}{(1 - k_2)a}$$

$$\text{Hence } H^\circ = \frac{K \times (1 - k_2)a}{\frac{k_4(b-a)}{n}}$$

The dissociation constant of the acid H_mA will be given by

$$K' = \frac{H^\circ \times H_{m-1}A'}{H_mA}$$

$$\text{and hence } K'_n = \frac{H^\circ \times A'}{HA'}$$

But the concentration of HA from $\text{Na}_{m-1}\text{HA} = k_3(b-a)/n$
because it ionises as $\text{Na}_{m-1}\text{HA} \rightleftharpoons \text{Na}_{m-1}^+ + \text{HA}'$

Also the concentration of $\text{A}' = k_1c - k_3(b-a)/n$
because Na_mA ionises as $\text{Na}_m\text{A} \rightleftharpoons \text{Na}_m^+ + \text{A}'$ and part of this forms
 Na_{m-1}HA , which $= k_3(b-a)/n$.

Hence substituting these values of H^+ , A' and HA we get the n th dissociation constant of the acid as

$$K'_n = \frac{\frac{K(1-k_2)a}{k_4(b-a)}}{n} \times \frac{k_1c - k_3(b-a)}{k_3 \frac{(b-a)}{n}}$$

$$= \frac{nK(1-k_2)a [nk_1c - k_3(b-a)]}{k_4 k_3 (b-a)^2} \quad \dots \quad (\text{A})$$

If we introduce the conception that the salts are completely ionised and acids do not ionise at all, then

$$k_1 = k_3 = k_4 = 1, \text{ and } k_2 = 0.$$

$$\text{Hence } K'_n = \frac{n \times K \times a \times [nc - (b-a)]}{(b-a)^2} \quad \dots \quad (\text{B})$$

and if acids are monobasic as considered by Dhar and Philip we can put $n=1$, and get

$$K'_n = \frac{K \times a(c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2} \quad \dots \quad (\text{ii})$$

the same formula as has been used in the calculation of the experimental results.

Thus we have succeeded in deriving a general formula and proving that Dhar (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **35**, 800) and Philip's (*J. Chem. Soc.* 1905, **87**, 987; 1909, **95**, 1466) formulae can be derived from it as special cases.

It is quite clear that this method of finding dissociation constant is only approximate at least for the acids whose basicity is greater than one and whose dissociation constant we assume, and higher the basicity, the less accurate are the results. Because in deriving this

formula we assume $H_nB = nH^\circ + B'$ which is never realised ; but there are various probabilities of ionisation

When $n=1$, the probability is only one and hence the calculated results are satisfactory.

In deriving the above general formula we have introduced the simplest conception. If we try to allow for all these probabilities the problem becomes very complex.

It is quite clear from the above formula why the formula

$$K' = \frac{K \times a(c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$$

breaks down when using carbonic acid gas, boric acid, arsenious acid etc., which are polybasic. If we employ the general formula in no case we get negative results. The correctness of the general formula is borne out by following results with potassium fluoride and boric acid, potassium chromate and boric acid, potassium fluoride and arsenious acid, etc. In all these case, we have already shown that we get negative results by the simple formula of Dhar and Philip. But our general formula gives positive and consistent results.

(i) *Dissociation constant of hydrofluoric acid with boric acid at 30°.*

$$K_1 = \frac{nK \times a(c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$$

But $n=3$ and $K=6.4 \times 10^{-10}$.

$$\text{Hence } K_1 = 3 \times 6.4 \times 10^{-10} \times a \frac{(3c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$$

a	b	$3c$	$b-a$	$3c-b \times a$	$K \times 10^{-9}$
1.029	1.566	0.9861	0.537	0.4491	1.05
„	1.330	0.4930	0.301	0.1920	1.39
„	1.205	0.2465	0.176	0.070	1.48

The dissociation constant increases with dilution.

(ii) *Dissociation constant of chromic acid with boric acid at 30°.*

$$K = \frac{3K' \times a \times (3c - b + a)}{(b - a)^2} \text{ for } n = 3.$$

a	b	3c	b - a	3c - b + a	K × 10 ⁻⁹
1.029	1.288	0.8051	0.209	0.0961	1.45
„	1.213	0.2837	0.184	0.0997	1.94
„	1.183	0.1418	0.084	0.0578	5.89

(iii) *Dissociation constant of hydrofluoric acid with arsenious acid at 30°.*

$$K = \frac{nK' \times a \times (nc - b + a)}{(b - a)^2} \text{ where } n = 3 \text{ for arsenious acid.}$$

a	b	3c	b - a	3c - b + a	K × 10 ⁻⁷
0.0284	0.2936	0.3463	0.0096	0.2367	2.2
„	0.3026	0.4929	0.0186	0.4743	1.17
„	0.3096	0.9861	0.0256	0.9605	1.2

(iv) *Dissociation constant of chromic acid with carbonic acid gas at 30°.*

$$K = \frac{nK \times a \times (nc - b + a)}{(b - a)^2} \text{ where } n = 2 \text{ for carbonic acid.}$$

a	b	2c	b - a	2c - b + a	K × 10 ⁻⁸
0.05714	0.3684	2.000	0.3112	1.688	1.184
„	0.2601	1.000	0.2029	0.7971	1.32
„	0.1973	0.500	0.1402	0.3598	1.25
„	0.1500	0.250	0.0928	0.1572	1.252
„	0.2541	0.7924	0.1970	0.5954	1.05
„	0.2460	0.6964	0.1888	0.5076	0.98
„	0.2637	0.8618	0.2066	0.6552	1.05
„	0.1760	0.4308	0.1188	0.3120	1.48
„	0.2148	0.4792	0.1572	0.3220	1.12

(v) *Dissociation constant of boric acid with carbonic acid.*

$$\text{We have } n = 2, \text{ hence } K' = \frac{2\{K \times a \times (2c - b + a)\}}{(b - a)^2}$$

Temp.	a	b	2c	b - a	2c - b + a	K × 10 ⁻⁸
17°	0.08377	0.3470	0.1540 × 2	0.2633	0.0447	3.24
16°	0.08641	0.4213	0.2156 × 2	0.3349	0.0963	4.45
18°	0.08123	0.5288	0.3080 × 2	0.4475	0.1685	4.1

These results are sufficient to prove the validity of our general

$$\text{formula } K = \frac{n'K \times a \times (nc - b + a)}{(b - a)^2}.$$

We now proceed to consider our second observation that the dissociation constant increases with dilution. We have already shown that $(b-a)$ is the amount of undissociated acid. In the simple formula $K = \frac{K' \times a \times (c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$ we have neglected the ionisation of the acid but this is only partially true. Also as the dilution increases, ionisation increases or the amount of undissociated molecules decreases. Therefore $(b-a)$ decreases with dilution and hence $c-b+a = \{c-(b-a)\}$ increase with dilution. Hence it is quite clear that $K = \frac{K' \times a(c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$ should increase with dilution.

The third observation that weaker the acid the lower is the dissociation constant obtained is now to be explained. Let us consider the simple formula,

$$K = \frac{K_1 \times a \times (c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$$

The lowering of K means that $(b-a)$ is too large, or the solubility b of the acid in the salt of the acid whose K is required is too great. In case of any acid such as benzoic acid—

But the concentration of $C_6H_5 \cdot COO'$ ions must always be $(b-a)$ and if the reaction (ii) occurs simultaneously, then $C_6H_5 \cdot CO_2H$ will be formed or number of $C_6H_5 \cdot COO'$ ions will fall as the acid ionises feebly. Hence more of the acid must dissolve so as to satisfy both the equations. Hence $(b-a)$ increases.

In case of carbonic acid which is weaker than benzoic acid, we have

or because the reaction (ii) also occurs, therefore as before more of carbon dioxide must dissolve to maintain equilibrium. But the degree of hydrolysis of $C_6H_5 \cdot CO_2K$ is much smaller than that of $KHCO_3$. Hence $(b-a)$ is greater in the case of H_2CO_3 , and consequently K is

much lower for H_2CO_3 than with $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{H}$. Thus weaker the acid we are working with, the lower is the dissociation constant obtained.

Thus we have succeeded in giving a theoretical interpretation for the experimental observations.

Summary.

(1) The dissociation constants of hypophosphorous, phosphorous, chromic, hydrofluoric, iodic, titanio, antimonic, boric, vanadic, tungstic and molybdic acids have been determined from solubility measurements of benzoic acid, carbonic acid and arsenious acid in the solution of their sodium or potassium salts.

(2) From the experimental results it has been observed that the formula $K = \frac{K_1 \times a \times (c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$ for determining the dissociation constants is specific for monobasic acids; where a = the solubility of the acid used in water, b = the solubility in the salt solution of concentration c , of the acid whose dissociation constant K is required, and K_1 = the dissociation constant of the acid used.

(3) The formula $K_n = \frac{nK(1-k_2)a\{nk_1c-k_3(b-a)\}}{k_4, k_3 (b-a)^2}$ for determining the n th dissociation constant has been deduced taking into consideration the basicity of the acid of which the dissociation constant is required and making due allowance for incomplete ionisation of the various substances used.

(4) It has been shown that the general formula becomes $K_n = \frac{nK \times a [nc - (b-a)]}{(b-a)^2}$ on the assumption that the salts ionise completely and that the weak acids do not ionise. On making further assumption that the acid, whose K is assumed, is monobasic, it reduces to $K_n = \frac{K \times a \times (c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$.

(5) It has been observed that the dissociation constant goes on increasing with dilution of the salt solution, and weaker the acid used, the lower is the value of the dissociation constant of the unknown acid. An explanation of these observed facts has been given on the basis of the formula $K_n = \frac{K \times a \times (c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$.